

REBOOT

EUROPEAN FILM COMPETITIVENESS

Last DMP

Project: Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness - REBOOT

Grant Agreement: 101094796 - HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01

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REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

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THE REBOOT PROJECT SUMMARY

This project aims to connect existing strengths, identify and overcome weaknesses, and plan for future competitiveness in the fields of policy, practice and experience. More concretely, the project's objectives are, firstly, to explore the long-standing strengths and pervasive gaps in European competitiveness and policies for competitiveness. This includes ways of measuring, analysing and evaluating the impact of policies and strategic pathways. Secondly, the project aspires to actively prepare for future audiences by exploring audience preferences and their generation, as well as modes of film content production. The latter are elements which today's youth will engage with in the coming decades as makers and consumers, as well as industry and policy leaders. Therefore, the consortium interrogates not only "what is" but also "what has been" and "what will be" from fresh perspectives.

REBOOT's ambition is to provide a full set of knowledge of the European film industry, which maximises its existing strengths, combined with strategic and tactical dimensions of action to optimise the potential held in European youth publics, understood both as emerging audiences and as citizens. Specifically, the ambition of the project combines several dimensions, which reinforce each other but are listed separately for analytical purposes (and in no particular order): a) increasing support for young people's engagement with European film; b) strengthening the place of the European Union (EU) in the global audiovisual economy, particularly in light of the rise of video on demand (VoD); c) supporting cultural diversity in the EU film industry; d) addressing the need for a different understanding of competitiveness and relevant indicators in this context; and e) recognising and supporting the importance for the EU of film and, more broadly, of the cultural and creative sector as a geopolitical asset.

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1. PURPOSE OF THIS DOCUMENT

This last Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the revised strategic approach of the Horizon Europe Project "Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness – REBOOT" to effectively manage, reuse, and make data-related decisions. This document replaces the two DMP documents, corrects both and includes updates on the last Data Management provided by our partners. The primary objective of this DMP is to promote transparency in data handling throughout the project's lifecycle and beyond. This document ensures that the consortium of REBOOT remains consistently updated, explicit, and maintains effective communication regarding data management. Any changes in the strategy regarding data is constantly discussed within the consortium.

2. DATA SUMMARY OF WPS

REBOOT produces several outputs within the project life cycle. Its deliverable classified as R= Report is mostly open access under CC BY and their dissemination level is PU. Project internal handbooks and plans like this version of a DMP are on the dissemination level sensitive to restrict public access since these documents serve for internal project management guidance.

REBOOTs outputs are:

- Deliverables:
 - DMP = Data Management Plan
 - Project first and interim DMPs are for internal usage (SEN)
 - Final DMP is publicly accessible (PU)
 - R = Documents, Reports:
 - Project Open Access Research Reports (PU)
 - Project internal management reports with access for the consortium only while project lifetime e.g., Project Management Handbook (SEN)
 - DEC = Website, Patent fillings, video
 - Project website (PU)
 - Press Releases and Press kits (PU)
 - Videos (PU)
 - DATA = Data sets, microdata
 - Public Dataset (PU)
 - Database (PU)

- OTHER:
 - Conferences (PU)
 - Workshops (PU)
- Other Outputs:
 - Blogposts publicly accessible via project website
 - Interview transcripts publicly accessible via archive after project termination (not defined yet)
 - with a high probability other public dissemination strategy (not defined yet)

REBOOT committed that open access has been the core principle for the reports of the project. The project aims to publish anonymised interview transcripts for future reuse in a selected archive by the end of the project, which will be open access under CC-BY. The open access databases produced in the framework of WP3 will be a major contribution of the project to open science, as will be the open access publications. In REBOOT, each task leader decides if data reuse is possible and, if so, proceeds to do so. REBOOT is an innovative project that will generate rich data for other scientific usage. Existing data such as secondary literature has been reused frequently during the project's lifetime. Raw data are collected through interviews, surveys, experiments, literature analysis, and other methods to achieve the following objectives:

- to generate data through multiple levels of investigation, providing a foundation and insights that are useful to raise the competitiveness of the EFI by involving the experts and stakeholders directly from the field.
- REBOOT employed a comprehensive analysis that considers not only the film making process but also the environment around filmmaking including cultural interactions, creative spaces, and innovative practices within the film industry.

To fulfil these objectives new and original data has been collected. REBOOT aimed to collect data to ensure future reuse and data utility is given not only to scientific staff but also to stakeholders of the field by providing its outputs as publicly as possible.

The following table shows how the Work Packages are structured regarding the methods, who and where original data will be gathered, and more information given why it is important to generate this new data.

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WP	METHODS	WHO/WHERE	WHAT	UPDATE JANUARY 2026
WP1 Management	No research			
WP2 Diachronic understandings of the 'competitiveness' and of the 'European' in EFI – UCM	Previous reports, desk research, semi-structured interviews (D2.2-2.4) Desk Research (D2.1)	<u>SPAIN:</u> Sp. Film Institute, VOD platforms, industry key players <u>POLAND:</u> National Film Institute, VOD platforms Industry key players <u>FINLAND:</u> Finnish film Foundation <u>BELGIUM:</u> Key industry stakeholders EU regulatory & policy documents	Scope: regional, national, EU Past - present - future Milestones, audiences, trends Interview questions from other WPs? EU regulatory & policy documents, conceptualisation of concepts related to film industry with a focus on competitiveness and cultural diversity.	No change of methods
WP3 The institutional context of the EU film industry – ELIAMEP	Mapping, desk research, interviews, methodological workshop (T3.1), database (D3.6)	<u>ELIAMEP</u> EU institutions, EU regulation, etc., instruments, greek regulations <u>SSSA</u> <u>ALL</u> Excel (created by ELIAMEP)	National mapping & assessment of legal and policy measures (T3.1) (SSSA) EU promotion of EFI	No change of methods

		<p><u>UC3M</u> Film institutions and regulations in Spain</p>	<p>internationally (ELIAMEP)</p> <p>Institutional analysis of different models for the promotion of EFI internationally (ULIEGE, all partners) (T3.4)</p> <p>Analysis of EU initiative promoting the EFI: The case of LUX Audience Award (JYU)</p> <p>Analysis of EU delegations' role in promoting the EFI: The case of the EU Film Festivals (JYU)</p> <p>Lived practices, principles, cultural institutions and the 'fringes' of filmmaking and consumption (UNIVIE)</p>	
<p>WP4 The framings and strategies of cinema professionals – ULIEGE</p>	<p>T4.1 (led by ULIEGE): desk research, semi-structured interviews, surveys.</p> <p>T4.2 (led by SSSA):</p>	<p>Associations of film/Audiovisual professionals</p> <p>EU level: Federation of European Screen Directors, EUROKINEMA,</p>	<p>Industrial and cinema professionals' understandings of the notions of "international market" and "EFI"</p>	<p>No change of methods</p>

	<p>Literature review, mapping, survey, workshop (in M29).</p> <p>T4.3 (led by EUR): desk research, semi-structured interviews, survey</p>	<p>Europa Distribution, European Association of Animation Cultures, Documentary Association of Europe, International Union of Cinemas, European Broadcasting Union, EUROVOD.</p> <p>EU Member States: Austria, Belgium (French and Flemish speaking community), Poland, Spain, France, Italy, Finland, Greece, and the Netherlands.</p> <p>T4.3: Beyond the EU: film professionals, that is, filmmakers, producers, distributors, other stakeholders (festival programmers and fund managers, exhibitors,</p>	<p>Views of European cinema professionals towards the “international market”</p> <p>T4.3: Views and perceptions of non-European cinema professionals towards the “European” in the EFI.</p>	
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		fundings, film festivals, co-production markets, etc) in Argentina, Brazil, Mexico (UC3M), South Korea (ULIEGE), Turkey (KHAS), South Africa (EUR)		
WP5 Building the future competitiveness – UNIVIE	<p>T5.1: Desk research, content analysis</p> <p>T5.2: Survey, quantitative analysis; qualitative content analysis</p> <p>T5.3: Experimental study</p> <p>T5.4: Ethnographic study, interviews</p> <p>T5.5: Focus group interviews</p> <p>T5.6: Report analysis</p> <p>T5.7: Policy analysis</p>	<p>UNIVIE UGENT, ELIAMEP, UCM, SSSA, UCA UW, KHAS, JYU</p> <p>Austria, Belgium, Greece, Spain, Italy, France, Poland, Turkey, Finland</p>	<p>T5.2: Survey on young people's film preferences in Europe</p> <p>T5.3: The cognitive skills developed in the creation and reception of content in Mixed Reality</p> <p>T5.3.1: The study of the cognitive abilities of young content creators in Mixed Reality</p> <p>T5.3.2: The experimental study of the reception practices of content in Mixed Reality by young audiences</p> <p>T5.4: Comparative studies on creative production</p>	No change of methods

			process for film music in Europe T5.5: Teenagers and Youth: tastes and interactions regarding transnational and European filmic content	
WP6 Indicators and recommendations – SSSA	Quantitative mapping			No change of methods
WP7 Dissemination	No research			
WP8 Ethics	No research			

Table 1: Research WP Methods and Operationalisation

3. FAIR DATA MANAGEMENT IN REBOOT

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

In REBOOT, data is identified by a persistent identifier, a DOI number, with publishing via Zenodo. To enhance visibility, reports are all provided with three keywords as part of the metadata. Metadata is generated by following the DataCite 4.0 standards.

Via Zenodo, metadata is collected through the portal and is harvestable/indexed. The following table shows which kind of metadata of each deliverable will be given.

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Licensing terms	CC BY 4.0
Author(s)	First responsible, afterwards alphabetical (Acronym of Institution after name)
Reviewer(s)	First responsible, afterwards alphabetical (Acronym of Institution after name)
Title	As per deliverable
Deliverable No.	D.X
WP No.	WPX (Acronym Leader)
Deliverable Lead	Acronym of University
Type	R=report, DEC=Video/website, DATA=Dataset, Other=Workshop/Press conference
Dissemination Level	PU/SEN
Version	1.X
Description	Short abstract
Keywords	At least 3 keywords
Language	eng

Table 2: Information included in the metadata

3.2. Making data accessible

REBOOT uploads its open access research outputs to the Zenodo repository as an example and requirement by the European Union's openAIRE provided general purpose repository, which meets requirements to be rated as a trustworthy repository. This ensures compliance with international standards within the consortium and acceptance within Horizon Europe, as per the presentation held by REBOOT's Project Officer on March 6, 2023. The provided metadata is incorporated into the data mask of Zenodo and subsequently published. The dissemination level of the outputs varies; most of them are open access, while others have restricted access, specifically the deliverables marked as "SEN" (sensitive), intended for internal use within the consortium. The decision to make sensitive deliverables open access is subject to a consortium vote after the conclusion of the REBOOT project.

Each deliverable uploaded to Zenodo automatically receives a DOI (Digital Object Identifier). Publication of the deliverables occurs promptly upon approval. To adhere to the Research

Data Management (RDM) Policies of each institute, publications are granted a dissemination level from the deliverable only if they do not contain any information that is legally prohibited, subject to contractual or ethical issues, or any other reasons that may limit access.

Publications, including reports and data, are licensed under CC BY 4.0, allowing users to share and adapt the content with proper attribution. The goal is to make all REBOOT publications accessible for a minimum of five years after the project's conclusion, with the potential for indefinite accessibility.

Reports are available in PDF format and downloadable, while data and datasets are provided in the most accessible format for the public to use.

3.3. Making data interoperable

In the REBOOT project, data is designed to be interoperable by avoiding specific assignments to uncommon or project-specific vocabularies. Instead, each publication and dataset is accompanied by a comprehensive description of its content. To achieve maximum interoperability, the consortium commits to providing as much follow-up information as possible for both reports and datasets. The selected Data Cite Metadata Schema 4.0 ensures a standardised approach to data interoperability.

To further enhance interoperability, REBOOT adopts common file formats like PDF, Excel, Word, and other widely used software formats typically accessible to the public. By employing these widely recognized formats, the project aims to promote seamless data sharing and collaboration among researchers and stakeholders.

3.4. Increase data re-use

REBOOT is committed to producing high-quality datasets that promote maximum reusability for future research. By providing open access, REBOOT aims to foster collaboration, enable knowledge sharing, and facilitate the validation and expansion of research findings by other researchers. To ensure responsible and transparent data sharing practices, all publications designated as public (PU) are provided under the CC BY 4.0 international license. This licensing approach allows users to freely share, adapt, and build upon the data, as long as appropriate attribution is given. By encouraging open and permissive usage, REBOOT seeks to inspire innovative research and further advancements in various fields. The publications are extensively documented in accordance with Metadata standards and follow-up documents. This documentation includes essential details about

the content, methodology, and context of the data, making it easier for other researchers to understand and utilise the information effectively.

As part of the quality assurance measures, the REBOOT Consortium has agreed upon a robust peer review process. For each deliverable produced by the project, two individuals within the consortium are assigned or volunteer to peer review the selected deliverable. These reviewers thoroughly analyse the content, provide valuable feedback, and offer constructive comments. The responsible authors for the deliverable then carefully review the comments and incorporate the feedback into their work if useful. This peer review system ensures the accuracy and credibility of the research outputs, maintaining high standards of scientific quality within the consortium.

To enhance the reusability of the data, REBOOT also takes additional measures during the project. These include creating data codebooks that describe the variables, data structure, and coding conventions used in the process of data analysing and gathering. Anonymization plans for the transcription of interviews are implemented to protect sensitive information and privacy while making the data suitable for broader reuse. Each partner responsible for the data collected is also held accountable for the anonymization of the content.

Readme files are provided if applicable, offering clear instructions on how to access, interpret, and use the data effectively. Data provenance is also documented, ensuring that the origin and sources of the data are well-documented and traceable. Moreover, data processing procedures are clarified, outlining how the data was collected, cleaned, and analysed. These measures collectively contribute to enhancing the usability and reusability of the data, promoting collaboration and knowledge advancement among researchers in the scientific community. This documentation is safely stored within the consortium and shared upon request.

4. FURTHER INFORMATION

4.1. Other research outputs

In addition to the official deliverables, REBOOT produces other research outputs, including blog posts, which are published on the project website. Moreover, all other research outputs generated throughout the project's duration are made available on the REBOOT website, and a summary of this material is also included in the quarterly newsletter as part of the dissemination activities

By disseminating research outputs through the REBOOT websites and newsletter editions, the aim was to promote transparency and knowledge sharing within the scientific community, stakeholders,

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and beyond. The REBOOT website and newsletters served as a central hub, providing researchers and stakeholders easy access to all research outputs.

By embracing a comprehensive approach to publishing and archiving research outputs, REBOOT enhanced the impact of its findings and fostered a culture of open science and collaborative research. Through these efforts, REBOOT has maximized the value of the project's contributions and advanced scientific knowledge across the field.

4.2. Allocation of resources

In REBOOT, data management responsibilities are divided among partners, encompassing tasks such as data transcription, utilising and ensuring open access to the collected data. The primary focus is on making the data easily accessible and reusable for future research, fostering a scientific advancement to accomplish the FAIR principle.

The following costs are planned for UNIVIE as coordinator in this regard:

- Transcriptions of interviews and focus groups, translation costs €3.500
- open access publications for UNIVIE 3x €10.000
- fieldwork, press conference, workshops €3.625
- open access publications for 3 anthologies and editing/proofreading for consortium 3x €15.000
- design of press kits, material for press conferences and workshops €4.000
- project management software €6.000
- for website, translations and maintenance, curation of blog and social media €7.500

4.3. Data security

Data security measures in REBOOT are implemented in accordance with the guidelines set forth by each partner institution involved. These provisions include aspects of data security, including data secure storage as well as the transfer of sensitive data.

Within the consortium, data transfer is conducted in a safe and secure manner through the use of a trusted file sharer, such as "Aconet File Sender" or "WeTransfer." This platform ensures that sensitive data is transmitted securely between partners, reducing the risk of unauthorised access. To ensure accountability and compliance with the anonymization process, the beneficiary responsible for the deliverable oversees the anonymization efforts conducted by each partner. This provides an additional layer of assurance that the data

handling practices are in line with GDPR, established guidelines, and data protection standards.

Data is safely stored in a repository to facilitate long-term preservation and findability. This means that data is stored in reliable and secure locations that have been designated by the consortium; for public access, Zenodo is used.

Back-up plan:

Data is stored on a local device to provide immediate access for work with the data. Additionally, three copies of the data are generated - two copies stored in separate USB devices or similar secure storage media, and one copy in a secured cloud environment provided by each partner institution. This multi-tiered backup strategy ensures against data loss.

Regarding the handling of personal data collected during the research process, each partner responsible for data collection has taken the necessary steps to anonymize the data. Anonymization ensured that any personally identifiable information is removed or encrypted, protecting the privacy of individuals involved in the research.

4.4. Ethics

REBOOT ensured that publicly classified data collected has been accessible for research. Before granting access to the publications, the reuse of data strictly adheres to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) guidelines and standard research ethics. The data remains accessible for a minimum of five years following the conclusion of the project. It is essential to note that the project's data is stored anonymously. All project researchers involved are held accountable to use proper consent forms "D8.1 - Consent forms for interviews and focus groups", rely on national and international obligations, and to obtain consent from every person involved in the research. All researchers have fulfilled the requirements under D8.2 "Consortium Ethics Survey checklist" published questionnaire and, in doubt, reach out to the Ethics Mentors appointed by the consortium.

For further details on the ethical requirements and guidelines, please refer to D8.5 "Approved Ethics Requirements Plan" of REBOOT's deliverables.

REBOOT emphasises the importance of data confidentiality and compliance with all relevant ethical considerations during the data sharing process.

5. RESEARCH WP DATA IN REBOOT

The following tables shows in detail which considerations are undertaken at each WPs. This shows planes, which are already set out for some of the tasks in REBOOT. Others which are not mentioned here are for the time being not yet decided.

5.1. WP2

WP2		Update January 2026
Use of pre-existing data (YES/NO) Which?	<p>T2.1. – YES EU documents (legislative and non-legislative) available on the websites of EU institutions</p> <p>T2.2. – YES Secondary sources - No: semi-structured interviews</p> <p>T2.3. – YES Secondary sources and NO: empirical qualitative research based on semi-structured interviews</p>	
Type of Data collected Interview, Survey, Experiment...	<p>T.2.1. Desk research/documents</p> <p>T.2.2: Desk research (specialised and grey literature) and semi-structured interviews with individual key players from the institutions under consideration</p>	

	T2.3: Desk research (specialised and grey literature), semi-structured interviews (on-site and online) with staff members and stakeholders of EFI	
Aim of the data collection For what reason will this exact data be needed? (Very short)	T2.1: Diachronic analysis of the development and evolution of EU action in the film sector T.2.2: Analysis of the impact of the EU film policies on the national contexts in the last 25 years T2.3: Analysis of key film industry stakeholders' experiences of recent technological, policy, and other changes in the European film landscape	
Process of data collection "Direct personal communication", "Email communication", "Open-source investigation"	T.2.2: Direct personal communication and email communication T2.3: Direct personal communication (on-site and online) and email communication	
Format of data collected .doc/docx (word) .xls/xlsx .ppt/pptx	T.2.1. .doc/docx (word) .xls/xlsx .ppt/pptx .pdf	T2.2: Video added T2.3: Video added

.pdf Photo /Video / Audio other (specify)	T2.2: .doc/docx (word) .ppt/pptx .pdf Audio T.2.3: .doc/docx (word) .ppt/pptx .pdf Audio	
Software needed for process with data MS Office, Adobe, MAXQDA, etc.	MS Office T2.2 MS Office CAQDAS (NVivo or Atlas.ti) T2.3: MS Office MAXQDA NVivo	
Storage of data/size of data Approx. (3 GB etc.) stored on Laptop/USB/repository/cloud	T2.2: Cloud	T2.2. and T2.3: Cloud and USB
Access of data within the consortium Who has access – Which partners and how? Who is contributing?	T2.1: ELIAMEP & ULIEGE T2.2: UCM, UW, JYU T2.3: UGENT, UCM	
Ethical considerations Ethical requirements	T2.2: Consent forms for interviews	T2.3: Consent forms for interviews

Table 3: Data considerations WP2

5.2. WP3

WP3	Update January 2026	
Use of pre-existing data (YES/NO) Which?	T3.1 - YES *International and regional legal instruments,	T3.2 – YES and NO secondary sources regarding LUX, selected films and interviews

	<p>*EU legislation and other documents, *National legislation, *Reports drafted and published in the context of the reCreating Europe project, *The open-access database on copyright flexibilities launched in the context of the reCreating Europe project.</p> <p>T3.3 – YES International instruments; Reports and strategies available on the website of European Commission</p> <p>T3.4 EU documents (legislative and non-legislative) available on the websites of national institutions; Market data related to the countries under study.</p> <p>T3.5 – YES EU documents (legislative and non-legislative) available on the websites of EU institutions</p> <p>T3.6 – YES and NO</p>	<p>T3.4 – YES and NO EU documents (legislative and non-legislative) available on the websites of national institutions. Supplementary and semi-structured interviews</p> <p>T3.5 – YES and NO EU documents (legislative and non-legislative) available on the websites of EU institutions and semi-structured expert interviews</p> <p>T3.6 – YES and NO Secondary sources regarding EU Film festivals Selected films and interviews with people managing EU film festivals</p>
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	<p>*secondary sources regarding EU Film festivals</p> <p>*selected films</p> <p>*interviews of people managing EU film festivals</p> <p>T3.2 – YES and NO</p> <p>*secondary sources regarding LUX</p> <p>*selected films</p> <p>*interviews</p>	
Type of Data collected Interview, Survey, Experiment...	<p>T3.1</p> <p>*Literature review, *empirical data collected via semi-structured interviews</p> <p>T3.3</p> <p>Literature review</p> <p>Empirical data collected via interviews</p> <p>T3.4</p> <p>Desk research/documents and semi-structured interviews with EU/national officials and policymakers</p> <p>T3.5 Desk research/documents and expert interviews with EU officials and policymakers</p> <p>T3.6 and T3.2 grey literature, films, interviews</p>	T3.3 Literature review/Interviews
Aim of the data collection	T3.1	

<p>For what reason will this exact data be needed? (Very short)</p>	<p>*A comprehensive mapping of the international, regional, and national legal tools governing the film-making industry, *Identifying the gaps in the legal landscape, *Suggesting improvement in the relevant EU and national laws.</p> <p>T3.2 Analysis of EU initiatives promoting the EFI</p> <p>T3.3 For the production of two reports on the Governance and public value and Recommendations on innovation for European film creators</p> <p>T3.4 Comparative analysis of different national institutional models towards the promotion of the EFI internationally.</p> <p>T3.5 Analysis of whether, and if so, how EU law and governance promotes the EFI on</p>	
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	<p>the international scene</p> <p>T3.6</p> <p>Analysis of the EU delegation's role in promoting the EFI</p>	
<p>Process of data collection</p> <p>"Direct personal communication", "Email communication", "Open-source investigation"</p>	<p>T3.1</p> <p>*Doctrinal research (systematic literature review) by using online search platforms,</p> <p>*Semi-structured interviews.</p> <p>T3.3</p> <p>Systematic literature review in 6 countries included in the research and online interviews with stakeholders</p> <p>T3.5.</p> <p>Semi-structured interviews to be carried out in person and online via direct personal communication and e-mail communication.</p> <p>T.3.6 and T3.2</p> <p>internet, VOD, direct personal communication</p>	
<p>Format of data collected</p> <p>.doc/docx (word)</p> <p>.xls/xlsx</p> <p>.ppt/pptx</p> <p>.pdf</p>	<p>For all WP3 tasks:</p> <p>.doc/docx (word)</p> <p>.xls/xlsx</p> <p>.ppt/pptx</p> <p>.pdf Audio</p>	

Photo /Video / Audio other (specify)		
Software needed for process with data MS Office, Adobe, MAXQDA, etc.	All WP3 tasks: MS Office T3.4: NVivo	Adobe added to all tasks
Storage of data/size of data Approx. (3 GB etc.) stored on Laptop/USB/repository/cloud	Cloud	
Access of data within the consortium Who has access – Which partners and how? Who is contributing?	All WP3 tasks: All participating partners T.3.6 All partners except in case of films only Kaisa Hiltunen from JYU	
Ethical considerations Ethical requirements	For the interviews conducted under T3.1, consent forms, data processing and privacy related authorisation has been required. For the interviews conducted under T3.3, consent forms, data processing and privacy related authorisation has been required. For the interviews conducted under T3.5, ethics approval from ELIAMEP's Research Ethics Committee has been required.	

	For the interviews conducted under T3.6 and T3.2, consent forms has been required.	
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Table 4: Data considerations WP3

5.3. WP4

WP4		Update January 2026
Use of pre-existing data (YES/NO) Which?	<p>T4.1 Market data and policy documents associated with EFI (Austria, Belgium (French and Flemish speaking community), Poland, Spain, France, Italy, Finland, Greece, and the Netherlands).</p> <p>T4.2 Literature, studies, and reports.</p> <p>T4.3 Market data and policy documents associated with the local film sectors (Argentina, Brazil, Mexico, South Korea, Turkey, South Africa)</p>	<p>T4.3 – YES Market data and policy documents associated with the local film sectors (Argentina, Brazil, Mexico, South Korea, Turkey, South Africa) added</p>
Type of Data collected Interview, Survey, Experiment...	<p>T4.1 Analysis of the views of European film professionals towards the international competitiveness of EFI *Semi-structured interviews with key</p>	<p>T4.3 Analysis of the views of international film professionals towards the EFI *Semi-structured interviews with key informants across the film supply chains in the selected international film markets *Common survey implemented across these international markets added</p>

	<p>informants across the film supply chains at the European level *Common survey implemented across nine EU MSs</p> <p>T4.3 Analysis of the views of international film professionals towards the EFI *Semi-structured interviews with key informants across the film supply chains in the selected international film markets *Common survey implemented across these international markets</p> <p>T4.2 *Identifying the obstacles faced by niche film markets, *Developing a set of best practices for the key stakeholders in the market.</p>	
<p>Aim of the data collection For what reason will this exact data be needed? (Very short)</p>	<p>T4.1 Analysis of the views of European film professionals towards the international competitiveness of EFI</p> <p>T4.3 Analysis of the views of international film</p>	

	<p>professionals towards the EFI</p> <p>T4.2 *Identifying the obstacles faced by niche film markets, *Developing a set of best practices for the key stakeholders in the market</p>	
<p>Process of data collection “Direct personal communication”, “Email communication”, “Open-source investigation”</p>	<p>T4.1 and T4.3 Open-source investigation and direct personal communication</p> <p>T4.2 *Doctrinal research (systematic literature review) by using online search platforms, *Semi-structured interviews.</p>	
<p>Format of data collected</p> <p>.doc/docx (word) .xls/xlsx .ppt/pptx .pdf Photo /Video / Audio other (specify)</p>	<p>T4.1 and 4.3 .doc/docx (word) .xls/xlsx .ppt/pptx .pdf Audio Video (to support WP7/dissemination)</p> <p>T4.2 .doc/docx (word) .xls/xlsx .ppt/pptx .pdf Audio Video (to support WP7/dissemination)</p>	
<p>Software needed for process with data</p>	<p>T4.1 and 4.3 MS Office NVivo</p>	

MS Office, Adobe, MAXQDA, etc.		
Storage of data/size of data Approx. (3 GB etc.) stored on Laptop/USB/repository/cloud	T 4.1 and T4.3 Cloud	
Access of data within the consortium Who has access – Which partners and how? Who is contributing?	T 4.1 and T4.3 All partners	
Ethical considerations Ethical requirements	T4.3 Consent forms for interviews Consent when filling in survey For the interviews conducted under T4.2 Consent forms, data processing and privacy related authorisation has been required.	

Table 5: Data considerations WP4

5.4. WP5

WP5		Update January 2026
Use of pre-existing data (YES/NO) Which?	For tasks WP5 T5.3, T5.3.1 and T5.3.2 – YES Use of articles on comparable empirical research on the field of classical cinema (“The school of Arthur Paul Shimamura”, Berkeley)	T5.7 – NO Unless desk research referred to literature review.
Type of Data collected Interview, Survey, Experiment...	T5.1 Grey literature, films, interview	

	<p>T5.2 Survey</p> <p>T5.3, T5.3.1 and T5.3.2 Empirical protocol application report</p> <p>T5.5 Focus groups</p>	
<p>Aim of the data collection For what reason will this exact data be needed? (Very short)</p>	<p>T5.1 Analysis of young people’s film preferences through YAA</p> <p>T5.2 Survey on young people’s film preferences</p> <p>WP5 T5.3, T5.3.1 and T5.3.2 (UCA) role was to explore the relationships between the dynamics of contemporary cinema and the creation / audience of virtual reality content watched and listened to in different immersive environments. Validation / invalidation of the hypothesis on the reinforcement of spectatorial practices based on feedback creation/exploitation of the informational load, comparatively: 2D contents and</p>	

	3D/360°/270° contents. T5.5 Teenagers and Youth: tastes and interactions regarding transnational and European filmic content	
Process of data collection “Direct personal communication”, “Email communication”, “Open-source investigation”	T5.1 Internet, VOD, email communication T5.2 Survey T5.3, T5.3.1 and T5.3.2 Viewing 3D/360 content in 3 environments, recording behaviours and responses T5.5 Focus group (in-person)	T5.2 Survey (Online, some partners used physical survey sheets)
Format of data collected .doc/docx (word) .xls/xlsx .ppt/pptx .pdf Photo /Video / Audio other (specify)	.doc/docx (word) .xls/xlsx .pdf .sav (spss)	
Software needed for process with data MS Office, Adobe, MAXQDA, etc.	MS Office Excel SPSS	
Storage of data/size of data	Cloud	

<p>Approx. (3 GB etc.) stored on Laptop/USB/repository/cloud</p>		
<p>Access of data within the consortium</p> <p>Who has access – Which partners and how? Who is contributing?</p>	<p>T5.1 JYU</p> <p>T5.2 All partners</p> <p>T5.3, T5.3.1 and T5.3.2 All partners</p> <p>T5.5 All partners have access to anonymised transcripts; each partner has access to the audio recordings of focus groups and participants' personal information</p>	
<p>Ethical considerations Ethical requirements</p>	<p>T5.2 Consents for survey (parental consent for minor); ethics clearance documents from host universities</p> <p>T5.3, T5.3.1 and T5.3.2 Consent for survey</p> <p>T5.5 Consents for focus groups (parental consent for minor); ethics clearance documents from host universities</p>	

Table 6: Data considerations WP5

5.5. WP6

WP6		Update January 2026
Use of pre-existing data (YES/NO) Which?	T6.3 – YES *This task is data provided by all WPs.	
Type of Data collected Interview, Survey, Experiment...	T6.3 *n/a	
Aim of the data collection For what reason will this exact data be needed? (Very short)	T6.3 *This task is aimed at compiling the data to be produced and provided by all WPs, in order to consolidate such data into a single file to be presented at the Final Conference of the project.	
Process of data collection “Direct personal communication”, “Email communication”, “Open-source investigation”	T6.3 *E-mail communication.	
Format of data collected .doc/docx (word) .xls/xlsx .ppt/pptx .pdf Photo /Video / Audio other (specify)	.doc/docx (word) .xls/xlsx .ppt/pptx .pdf	
Software needed for process with data MS Office, Adobe, MAXQDA, etc.	MS Office	
Storage of data/size of data Approx. (3 GB etc.) stored on Laptop/USB/repository/cloud	Cloud	

Access of data within the consortium	All partners	
Who has access – Which partners and how? Who is contributing?		
Ethical considerations Ethical requirements		

Table 7: Data considerations WP6

6. CHANGES PER PARTNER JANUARY 2026

Institution	Changes 2026
UNIVIE	No changes
ULIEGE	No changes
ELIAMEP	No changes
UCM	No changes
KHAS	Contribution to WP5
EUR	No changes
UGENT	No changes
UC3M	No changes
SSSA	No changes
UCA	No changes
JYU	No changes
UW	No changes

Table 8: Changes per partner, January 2026

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Disclaimer

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